

Utilization of manure and liquid organic fertilizer with different concentration on growth and production of chili (*Capsicum frutescens* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Chili is a horticultural crop that is used as food and industry materials. This research aimed to observe the response of different dosage of cow manure and liquid organic fertilizer (LOF) based on local microorganism (LoM) from papaya on chili growth and production. It was conducted at CV. Tani Makmur's screenhouse, Pati regency, Central Java from January to May 2018. The experiment utilized a completely randomized design in 5 x 4 factorial arrangement of treatments with 3 replications. The first factor was dosage of cow manure which consist of 5 levels: A₀ = without manure, A₁ = 5 ton/ha, A₂ = 10 ton/ha, A₃ = 15 ton/ha and A₄ = 20 ton/ha. The second factor was LOF concentration which consist of 4 levels: B₀ = without LOF, B₁ = 450 ml/plant, B₂ = 900 ml/plant, and B₃ = 1,350 ml/plant. The observed parameters were plant height, number of leaves, flowering age, number of fruit, fruit weight, and dry weight of biomass. Data were subjected to the analysis of variance test followed by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). Result showed that interaction between 20 ton/ha dosage of cow manure and 1,350 ml/plant of LOF significantly increased plant height, fruit weight and dry weight of biomass, but it had no effect on number of leaves, flowering age and number of fruit.

Keywords: chili, cow manure, LOF, plant growth, plant production

INTRODUCTION

Chili (*Capsicum frutescens* L.) is one of the leading agricultural commodities in Indonesia which is used as a material for household consumption, ingredients in the food processing industry, medicines and cosmetics. The needsof chili in Indonesia for direct consumption and other uses increased from 703 tons in 2016 to 885 tons in 2017 (Sabarella et al., 2017).

The consumption of chili will increase continuously along with population growth in Indonesia (Hasanuddin and Lisnawita, 2017). Effort to increase chili productivity and improve soil fertility is by using cow manure.

Cow manure contains macro nutrients such as 0.5% N, 0.25% P₂O₅, 0.5% K₂O with water content 0.5%, magnesium 0.33%, C-organic 6.62%, C/N ratio 10.18 and 11.41% organic matter content (Andayani and Sarido, 2013; Hafizah and Rabiatul, 2017). Sahera et al. (2012) concluded that cow dung fermented into fertilizer affect the leaf area, number of flowers and planting fruit, fresh plant weight and production (ton/ha). Ajak and Taolin (2016) states that cow manure produces the highest production of chili, compared to chicken manure and pig manure.

In addition to cow fertilizer which is applied as basal fertilizer increase productivity of chili plants which can be supported by Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) from papaya fruit as LMO. LOF can support fertilizer in providing growth and production of chili. The LMO from papaya contains macro nutrients (N, P, K, Ca and Mg) and micro nutrients that can fulfil the standards set by the government as LOF (Handayani et al. 2015). Agricultural waste such as unsuitable fruits can be processed into LMO to increase waste value, and reduce environmental pollution (Juanda et al. 2011). Rahayu (2017) states that LOF application from papaya as LMO affects the production of chili. LOF can improve soil conditions, support plant growth, and do not provide side effects in long term. However, the LOF application needs to pay attention to the right concentration or dosage for the plant (Belova et al., 2010).

This study was aimed to determine the effect of cow manure and LOF in different dosages on the growth and production of chili.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted at the greenhouse of CV. Tani Makmur, Rejoagung Village, Trangkil Subdistrict, Pati District, Central Java Province, Integrated Laboratory of Agricultural Environment Research Institute, Pati, Central Java, and the laboratory of Plant Ecology and Production, Faculty of Animal and Agricultural Sciences, Diponegoro University, Semarang, Indonesia, from January to May 2018.

Materials

The materials used in this study include chili seeds (Dewata variety), soil, cow manure, rotten papaya, molasses, rice, and water. The tools used in this research are tray, 60 polybags, manual and analytic scales, shovel, blender, sprayer, labels, envelopes, oven, camera and stationery.

Methods

The first stage was the manufacture of manure, carried out by collecting cow dung from cattle farms around CV. Tani Makmur. LOF made for 15 days, it was made using 0.5 kg of rotten papaya fruit that were smoothed, mixed with 1 liter of rice washing water and 0.1 liter of molasses. Planting had been done 35th days after seedling. It was planted in polybags containing 8 kg of soil and cow manure as base fertilizer with pre-planned treatment dose, polybags was arranged with a spacing of 50 x 50 cm. The chili plant maintenance phase done by watering the plants every day (± 500 ml/plant) or adjusting the weather and environmental conditions. Fertilization treatment with LOF given at 1st week after planted. It was done once a week with LOF concentration adjusted to the treatment. Harvesting stage was carried out at the age of the plant reaches 85 days, or marked with reddish chili fruit, it was done up to 4 times at intervals of 3 days. Parameters measured were plant height, number of leaves, age of flowering, fruit weight, number of fruits and dry weight of biomass.

Experimental Design and Statistical Analysis

This study was conducted using a completely randomized design (CRD) in 5 x 4 factorial arrangement of treatments with 3 replications. The first factor was the application of cow manure, namely A₀: without manure, A₁: 5 tons/ha, A₂: 10 tons/ha, A₃: 15 tons/ha, and A₄: 20 tons/ha. The second factor was the application of LOF, B₀: without LOF, B₁: 50% recommendation dosage or 450 ml/plant, B₂: 100% recommendation dosage or 900 ml/plant, and B₃: 150% recommendation dosage or 1,350 ml/plant. Data were analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) to know the effect of treatments and continued with Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the 5% level ($P < 0.05$) to evaluate the differences among treatments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant Height

The results of variance analysis showed that the manure and interaction between manure and LOF had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$), but application of LOF did not affect the plant height. The results of Duncan's multiple range tests are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Height of Chili Plant at 5th Week on Different Dosage of Cow Manure and LOF Application.

Cow Manure (ton/ha)	Dosage	LOF Dosage (ml/plant)				Average
		0 (B ₀)	450 (B ₁)	900 (B ₂)	1,350 (B ₃)	
------(cm)-----						
0 (A ₀)		16.7 ^f	25.5 ^{de}	25.2 ^{de}	32.1 ^{abcde}	24.9 ^b
5 (A ₁)		34.6 ^{abcde}	34.4 ^{abcde}	31.1 ^{bcde}	27.3 ^{cde}	31.8 ^a
10 (A ₂)		29.6 ^{bcde}	32.4 ^{abcde}	36.2 ^{abc}	31.4 ^{bcde}	32.4 ^a
15 (A ₃)		38.6 ^{ab}	34.7 ^{abcd}	35.1 ^{abc}	31.2 ^{bcde}	34.9 ^a
20 (A ₄)		32.3 ^{abcde}	36.9 ^{ab}	31.6 ^{abcde}	41.1 ^a	35.5 ^a
Average		30.4	32.8	31.8	32.6	

Notes: Different superscripts in the same column and interaction column show significant differences (P <0.05)

Based on Table 1. At A₀ (without manure), maximum plant height was found in B₃ (32.1 cm) and minimum was found in B₀. At A₁ (5 tons/ha of manure), there were no enhancement on plant height at all LOF dosage, the same results were found at A₂ and A₃. Treatment of manure at A₄ (20 tons/ha of cow manure) with the addition of LOF 1,350 ml/plant (B₃) gave the maximum plant height and minimum was found in B₀. This is related to the fulfillment of plant nitrogen requirement in the soil due to fertilization treatment. Maruli *et al.* (2012) stated that nitrogen is an element needed for the formation of vegetative parts of plants such as leaves, stems and roots. Increased plant growth due to fertilization occurs when all nutrients needed by plants are in sufficient quantities and are in a form that is ready to be absorbed by plants (Nurahmi *et al.* 2011).

The LOF application does not give effect to the height of the chili plant, this is because the nitrogen contained in the LOF cannot be absorbed by the plant optimally. The content of nitrogen in LOF is low (0.32%), causing the release of nutrients requires a longer time. This is consistent with the opinion of Budiyan *et al.* (2016) that fertilizer with low nitrogen content requires longer mineralization.

Number of leaves

The results of the variance analysis showed that different dosage of cow manure gave a significant effect (P <0.05) on the number of leaves of chili plants, while the LOF dosage treatment and interaction between the two factors did not significantly affect the number of plant leaves. Duncan's multiple range test results of manure dosage can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Number of Leaves of Chili Plants at 5th Week on Different Dosage of Cow Manure and LOF Application

Cow Dosage (ton/ha)	Manure	LOF Dosage (ml/plant)				Average
		0 (B ₀)	450 (B ₁)	900 (B ₂)	1,350 (B ₃)	
0 (A ₀)		14	14	11	22	15 ^c
5 (A ₁)		33	25	19	14	23 ^b
10 (A ₂)		22	34	22	27	26 ^b
15 (A ₃)		40	35	34	29	35 ^a
20 (A ₄)		20	27	24	30	25 ^b
Average		26	27	22	24	

Notes: Different superscripts in the same column show significant differences ($P < 0.05$)

Based on Table 2. Treatment at 15 tons/ha of manure (A₃) gave the highest number of leaves, then the number of leaves decreased at 20 tons/ha (A₄). This shows that 15 tons/ha of manure (A₃) is the optimal dosage to increase the number of leaves, more than these dosages can cause the number of leaves to decrease. The higher the fertilizer dosage given, the nutrient content absorbed by plants is higher in accordance with the limits of crop needs. The treatment of cow manure that consist nitrogen can support the increase the number of chili plant leaves. Lumbanraja (2012) states that nitrogen in cow manure plays an important role in the formation of leaf green matter, then used in photosynthesis to produce carbohydrates as food that will be used in the growth process. Priyani *et al.* (2017) added that nitrogen can increase the amount of chlorophyll and photosynthesis rate so that eventually the photosynthate formed will be sufficient for the growth of plant organs such as leaves.

Flowering age

The results of the analysis of variance showed that the treatment of cow manure had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on the flowering age of chili. There is no effect on LOF application and interaction between two factors on the age of flowering of chili. Duncan's multiple range test presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Flowering Age of Chili Plants with Different Dosage of Cow Manure and LOF Application

Cow Manure Dosage (ton/ha)	LOF Dosage (ml/plant)				Average
	0 (B ₀)	450 (B ₁)	900 (B ₂)	1,350 (B ₃)	
0 (A ₀)	29	29	29	29	29 ^a
5 (A ₁)	26	26	26	26	26 ^b
10 (A ₂)	20	20	19	20	20 ^c
15 (A ₃)	18	19	18	19	18 ^d
20 (A ₄)	18	17	17	16	17 ^e
Average	22	22	22	22	

Notes: Different superscripts in the same column show significant differences ($P < 0.05$)

The results of the study (Table 3) showed that 20 tons/ha of manure (A₄) gave the fastest flowering age of chili plant among other treatments, namely on the 17th day after planting. The higher the dosage of manure given, the flowering age of chili plant will be faster. This is because cow manure can provide phosphor to help the formation of chili. The phosphor content in cow manure is 0.88%; increasing amount of manure can increase the available phosphor in the soil for flowering. This is in accordance with Baharuddin's opinion (2016) that flowering age is affected by phosphor obtained and utilized by plants from fertilization. Safei *et al.* (2014) states that the availability and uptake of phosphor by plants can further accelerate the flowering process and improve crop quality.

Number of fruits

The results of the analysis of variance showed that interaction between two factors, manure and LOF at different dosage had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on the number of fruits/plant. The results of Duncan's multiple range test presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Number of Chili Fruit with Different Dosage of Cattle Fertilizer and LOF Application

Cow Manure Dosage (ton/ha)	LOF Dosage (ml/plant)				Average
	0 (B ₀)	450 (B ₁)	900 (B ₂)	1,350 (B ₃)	
0 (A ₀)	5 ^k	9 ^{jk}	11 ^{jk}	14 ^{ij}	10 ^e
5 (A ₁)	7 ^k	12 ⁱ	19 ⁱ	18 ⁱ	14 ^d
10 (A ₂)	24 ^g	28 ^{gh}	32 ^{fg}	34 ^{ef}	29 ^c
15 (A ₃)	39 ^{de}	51 ^c	57 ^b	64 ^a	53 ^a
20 (A ₄)	34 ^{ef}	41 ^d	55 ^{bc}	60 ^b	47 ^b
Average	22 ^d	28 ^c	35 ^b	38 ^a	

Notes: Different superscripts in the same interaction column, row and column show significant differences (P < 0.05)

Based on Table 4. At A₀ (without manure), maximum number of fruits was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₁ (5 ton/ha cow manure), maximum number of fruits was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₂ (10 ton/ha cow manure), maximum number of fruits was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₃ (15 ton/ha cow manure), maximum number of fruits was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₄ (20 ton/ha cow manure), maximum number of fruits was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). Treatment of manure at 15 tons/ha and treatment of LOF at 1,350 ml/plant (A₃B₃) gives the highest amount of chili. This indicates that the addition of cow manure, LOF and a combination of both fertilizers can sufficient the nutrient needs of chili plant. Fruit formation in plants is supported by the presence of phosphor and potassium nutrients in the soil from fertilization. The phosphor content in manure is 0.88% and in LOF is 0.25%, so that fertilization can increase the availability of phosphor in the soil, help to accelerate the flowering and ripening process of fruit. This is in accordance with Bukhari's (2013) opinion that the ripening process of fruit is influenced by the levels of phosphor absorbed by plants from the soil, phosphor deficiency causes the quality and quantity of crop yield to decrease. Wahyuningratri et al. (2017) states that phosphor and potassium contained in the soil from the addition of fertilizers play an active role in the generative phase. Phosphor accelerates flowering, seeds and fruit ripening process, while potassium functions to strengthen the body parts of the flower and fruit so as not to fall easily.

The number of fruits increased in 15 tons/ha manure treatment (A₃), then decreased at a dosage of 20 tons/ha (A₄). This shows that plants still absorb nutrients according to their capacity or efficiency. Maruli et al. (2012) stated that the higher the LOF concentration given, the higher the nutrient content absorbed in accordance with the limit of the nutrient absorption capacity of chili plants. Fathini et al. (2014) stated that in order to obtain optimal production, nutrient levels should be in accordance with the needs of plants, excess nutrient levels can inhibit plant growth and reduce economic value.

Fruit Weight

The results of the analysis of variance showed that interaction between two factors, manure and LOF different dosage had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) of the weight of chili fruit. The results of Duncan's multiple range test presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Weight of Chili Fruit with Different Dosage of Cow Manure and LOF Application

Cow Manure Dosage (ton/ha)	LOF Dosage (ml/plant)				Average
	0 (B ₀)	450 (B ₁)	900 (B ₂)	1,350 (B ₃)	
	------(g)-----				
0 (A ₀)	11.25 ⁱ	18.95 ^h	36.3 ^s	57.42 ^{cd}	30.98 ^e
5 (A ₁)	11.65 ^{ij}	19.2 ^h	37.6 ^{fg}	56.89 ^d	31.33 ^e
10 (A ₂)	12.17 ^{ij}	20.07 ^h	39.03 ^{efg}	60.32 ^{bc}	32.89 ^b
15 (A ₃)	12.84 ^{ij}	19.56 ^h	40.23 ^{ef}	63.56 ^b	34.04 ^b
20 (A ₄)	14.85 ⁱ	20.84 ^h	41.56 ^e	69.46 ^a	36.67 ^a
Average	12.55 ^d	19.72 ^c	38.94 ^b	61.53 ^a	

Notes: Different superscripts in the same interaction column, row and column show significant differences ($P < 0.05$)

Based on Table 5. At A₀ (without manure), maximum fruit weight was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₁ (5 ton/ha of cow manure), maximum fruit weight was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₂ (10 ton/ha of cow manure), maximum fruit weight was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₃ (15 ton/ha of cow manure), maximum fruit weight was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). At A₄ (20 ton/ha of cow manure), maximum fruit weight was found in B₃ (1,350 ml/plant of LOF) and minimum was found in B₀ (without LOF). Treatment at 20 tons/ha cow manure and 1,350

ml/plant of LOF (A₄B₃) gave the highest fruit weight (69.46 g). This shows that the availability of nutrients, especially potassium due to a combination of fertilization can be absorbed and utilized by plants to increase fruit weight, potassium help plant for thickening fruit flesh. This is in accordance with the opinion of Ortas (2013) which states that potassium can increase the size and weight of fruit. Potassium can increase turgor pressure to support the process of distributing nutrients from leaves to chili fruit (Taufik et al., 2013).

The higher dosage of manure and LOF given, independently able to increase the weight of chili. Prasetyo (2014) states that the treatment of cow manure can provide potassium supply and increase the yield of red chili. Various dosages of LOF can increase fruit weight per plant, fruit length and diameter (Ignatius et al., 2014).

Dry Weight of Biomass

The results of the analysis of variance showed that the interaction between two factors and cow manure fertilizer had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on the parameters of dry weight of biomass, while the LOF treatment did not show any significant effect. The results of Duncan's multiple range test presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Dry Weight of Biomass on Different Dosages of Cow Manure and LOF Applications.

Cow Manure Dosage (ton/ha)	LOF Dosage (ml/plant)				Average
	0 (B ₀)	450 (B ₁)	900 (B ₂)	1,350 (B ₃)	
	------(g)-----				
0 (A ₀)	8.33 ^g	8.00 ^g	8.17 ^g	8.25 ^g	8.19 ^e
5 (A ₁)	9.17 ^e	9.00 ^e	9.17 ^e	9.17 ^{ef}	9.13 ^d
10 (A ₂)	11.17 ^d	11.75 ^d	11.67 ^d	11.33 ^d	11.48 ^c
15 (A ₃)	14.58 ^c	14.33 ^c	14.33 ^c	14.58 ^c	14.46 ^b
20 (A ₄)	23.33 ^b	23.67 ^b	24.42 ^a	24.67 ^a	24.02 ^a
Average	13.316	13.35	13.55	13.60	

Notes: Different superscripts in the same column and interaction column show significant differences ($P < 0.05$)

Based on Table 6. At A₀ (without manure), there were no enhancement on plant height at all LOF dosage, the same results were found at A₁, A₂ and A₃. Treatment of manure at 20 tons/ha and treatment of LOF dosages at 1,350 ml/plant (A₄B₃) gave maximum average dry weight of biomass (24.67 g). This is related to the availability of nitrogen nutrients contained in the soil and

absorbed by plants. The higher the fertilization dosage of both factors shows the heavier the plant dry weight. In the opinion of Islam et al. (2017), differences in plant weight occur due to the availability of nitrogen through fertilization. Baharuddin (2016) states that increased photosynthetic activity will produce more photosynthate so that the dry weight of the plant will increase. Amiroh (2017) states that nutrients in fertilizers can increase the content of organic and inorganic substances in cells, these substances will be converted into proteins, nucleic acids and polysaccharides, which then form tissues and organs, so that the wet and dry weight of plants increases.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study concluded that the treatment combination of 20 tons/ha of cow manure with 1,350 ml/polybag of LOF gave the highest effects on plant height, fruit weight, and dry weight of biomass. The treatment of 20 tons/ha of manure gave the best outcomes on plant height, flowering age, fruit weight, and dry weight of biomass. The treatment of 1,350 ml/polybag of LOF gave the highest outcomes for its number of fruit and fruits weight.

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